

INTERFACIAL EVALUATION OF TRANSPARENT AND CONDUCTIVE CNT AND ITO COATINGS ON PET SUBSTRATES WITH NANO-STRUCTURAL ASPECTS

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1 Introduction

Recently, carbon nanomaterials (CNMs) have attracted with considerable attention in the research and industrial field due to their unique mechanical and electrical properties for multi-functional purpose [1]. Carbon nanocomposites have high stiffness, strength and good electrical conductivity at relatively low concentrations of reinforcing CNMs. Conductivity and high aspect ratio of carbon nanotube (CNT) are attractive properties for producing conductive composites with a minimum of material. The electrical conductivity of carbon nanotube is very high. Films made of CNTs also possess a low sheet resistance and exhibit an optical transmittance in the visible spectrum comparable to that of commercial indium tin oxide (ITO). This is surprising as it has been demonstrated that SWCNT films can exhibit conductivity and transmittance values comparable to conventional ITO. In particular, transparent conducting CNT coatings on flexible substrates such as polyethylene terephthalate (PET) can be used as ITO/PET electrodes in chemical and mechanical stability and exhibit a wider electrochemical window.

The feature can be used for coatings to get transparent and conductive networks. For this, various techniques have been investigated such as, dip-coating, spraying, spin-coating, vacuum filtration, Langmuir-Blodgett deposition, and electrophoretic deposition (EPD). Among them, the dip coating provides CNT thickness control easily and it offers a low cost, simple process, and uniform deposition. However, it takes a number of iterative dip-coating steps to ensure sufficient electrical conductivity [2].

Contact angle measurement is widely used for investigating surface characteristics on various materials. The surface free energy of a material controls its adhesion, adsorption, lubrication, joint strength, wettability, etc. The wettability of solid surfaces is an important problem in surface science and practical applications. Young's equation is used to describe the wettability, where 90° acts as the critical contact angle (CA) to divide the concept of hydrophobic and hydrophilic properties. The macroscopic Young-Dupre equation correlates the contact angle to the surface and interfacial tensions. In the research reported here, transparent and conductive carbon nanotube coatings were fabricated, by a dip-coating method on polyethylene terephthalate (PET) substrates. The changes of electrical and optical properties of these CNT coatings depended mainly on the number of dip-coatings and the CNT concentration. Interfacial properties were investigated for CNT and ITO coatings, on PET substrates, by measurement of electrical resistance on specimens under cyclic loading [3].

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Multi-wall carbon nanotube (MWCNT, IJin Nanotech Co., Korea) and ITO (I25R, Mijitech, Korea) as coating materials was used. To prepare CNT solution in coating process, 2-propanol was used as dispersion solvents of CNT.

2.2 Electrical resistance measurement

The CNT coated PET films were washed using distilled water after the dip-coating process and then

dried in an oven to more completely remove the solvent in the coating. The surface resistance of the CNT coated PET was determined using a four-point method. The surface resistance was then calculated using a dual configuration method, and compared with the results of a single configuration method, to eliminate edge effects and to obtain more uniform electrical resistances. This dual configuration method is based on the equations:

$$R_s = k_a \times R_a \quad (1)$$

$$k_a = -14.696 + 25.173 \left(\frac{R_a}{R_b} \right) - 7.872 \left(\frac{R_a}{R_b} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

2.3 Fabrication of CNT coating

Acid-treated CNT was dispersed in 2-propanol solvent for 12 hours under sonication. 0.05 wt% CNT solution was used and the CNT coated layer was fabricated with different dipping cycles. Pre-cleaned PET film in ethanol solvent was used as a substrate and sonicated in double distilled water, and then finally rinsed intensively. After the dip-coating process, the specimen was dried in the clean-oven at 60 °C to evaporate remaining water completely.

2.4 Wettability measurement

Tensiometric method is the most versatile and suitable way for static and dynamic contact angle measurement on flat plate and filament. Dynamic contact angles of PET substrate with CNT coating were measured using Wilhelmy plate technique (Sigma 70, KSV Co., Finland). Four dipping liquids double purified water, formamide, ethylene glycol and diiodomethane were used. Dynamic contact angle, surface energies, donor and acceptor components, polar and dispersive free energy terms of PET substrates with different cyclic coating CNT coating were measured. The basic equation for Wilhelmy plate method is as follow

$$F = mg + P\gamma_{lv} \cos\theta - F_b \quad (3)$$

where F is total force, m is the mass of plate, g is acceleration of gravity, F_b is buoyancy force, P is fiber perimeter.

2.5 Transmittance measurement

Transmittance of the coatings was measured using an Ultraviolet-Visible (UV) Spectrophotometer. This

instrument measures the intensity of light after it passing through a specimen (I) and compares it to the intensity of light before it passes through the specimen (I_0). The ratio I/I_0 (T), called the transmittance, is usually expressed as a percentage:

$$T = \frac{I}{I_0} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Morphology of CNT coating by dip-coating

CNT coating networks were observed using SEM technique. Figure 1 shows the FE-SEM photos for surface morphology of CNT coated PET films with: (a) one cyclic coating, (b) dual cyclic coating, and (c) triple cyclic coating. The concentration of CNT dispersed solution is 0.05 wt%, PET films were washed using ethanol solvent under sonication before the dip-coating process. In the PET film with one cyclic coating case, CNT was coated on the PET film just partially, the density of CNT networks was much lower than others. Moreover, dual cyclic coated specimen exhibited the medium state, density of CNT networks increased compared with first specimen. On the other hands, in the triple cyclic coating case, the PET film was coated with CNT completely and more densely than the others. Since surfactant did not use in the CNT networks, the CNTs contact each other directly, which greatly enhances the electrical conductivity.

Fig. 1. FE-SEM photos of CNT coatings with different cycles by dip-coating

3.2 Transparent properties

Transparent properties were measured using UV spectrum test after specimen was dried again. Figure 2(a) exhibits the correlation between transmittance versus wavelength of PET substrate with different cyclic coating. The neat PET film was set as standard for 100% transparency. As expected, transmittance decreased with increasing the cyclic coating. The transmittance of CNT coated PET films were in the range of 78 to 90%. As the dipping

number increased, the density and thickness of CNT networks could increase as well. The CNT coated PET film with triple cyclic coating exhibited the lowest transmittance on the visible light range.

Fig. 2. Transmittance and electrical properties

3.3 Electrical properties

Figure 2(b) shows the surface resistance of CNT coated PET films with different dipping cycles. The surface resistance value of triple cyclic coated specimen was much lower than one cyclic coated specimen, and the result of surface resistance is consistent with transmittance test. As the dipping cycle increased, the surface resistance decreased, which means the CNT coated PET film with triple cyclic coating is more conductive than the others. Based on values of coefficient of variation, the CNT coated specimen with triple cyclic coating is more uniform than one dipping cycle case. It is because of as cyclic coating increased, the density and thickness of CNT networks were increased together, so there were more contact points in the networks.

3.4 Wettability measurement

Figure 3 shows optical photographs of water droplets in static contact angle measurements for (a) neat PET film, (b) PET film with one cyclic coating, (c) PET film with dual cyclic coating, and (d) PET film with triple cyclic coating. CNT coated specimens were taken some pre-preparing process as before, static contact angles were measured after washing and dry process. The diameter of water droplets were about 2mm. Compare with the other CNT coated specimen, the PET film with triple cyclic coating exhibit a more hydrophobic property, with a static contact angle of about 100°, whereas the static contact angle for the neat PET film is much lower. Static contact angles of CNT coated PET films with different cyclic coating increased gradually as the cyclic coating increased. The

hydrophobic properties of CNT coated film were due to the microstructures of CNT network on the surface.

Fig. 3. Static contact angle of CNT coatings

Fig. 4. Dynamic contact angle of CNT coatings with different cyclic coating

Figure 4(a) shows plots of dynamic contact angle of CNT coated PET films on double distilled water with three different cyclic coating. The specimen with triple cyclic coating exhibited more hydrophobic nature than one or dual cyclic coating. For comparison, contact angles of all CNT coated PET films were more than neat PET film. Especially, dynamic contact angles were agreed with static contact angles as shown in Figure 3. Figure 4(b) shows the correlation between CNT cyclic coatings *versus* dynamic contact angles. The dynamic contact angle increased obviously in initial three cyclic coating. After that, the dynamic contact angles of PET films with more cyclic coating were obtained nearly as a constant.

3.5 Morphology of coatings by spray-coating

Figure 5 shows FE-SEM photographs illustrating the surface morphology of: (a) CNT coating, and (b)

ITO coating on PET films deposited by spray coating. The thickness of the coating layer was controlled by varying the CNT or ITO concentration and volume deposited of the coating solution. Both CNT and ITO coatings exhibited good electrical conductivity due to abundant contact points of the CNTs or ITO powders.

Fig.5. FE-SEM photographs of the surface morphology: (a) CNT coating, and (b) ITO coating

3.6 Cyclic loading tests

Figure 6 shows some results and changes in surface resistance and load for ITO and CNT coated specimens during cyclic straining. The cyclic loading was at constant 1% strain amplitude at 1 Hz. There was little if any change in surface resistance for the CNT coated specimens even after 2000 cycles. For the ITO coated specimens, the surface resistance increased significantly during the first 1000 cycles before leveling off and remaining essentially constant. These observations are attributed to differences in micro-cracking of the coatings and the associated lose in electrical contact points. From these curves one might infer that the network of CNTs in the CNT coating provided a stable linking structure, even under fatigue tests. Such micro-cracking is apparent in Figure 7.

Fig.6. Fatigue test of ITO and CNT coatings on PET

Fig. 7. Schematic sketches of microcracking: (a) CNT, (b) ITO coatings

4 Conclusions

Transmittance and conductive properties of CNT coated PET films were investigated using UV spectrum test and surface resistance measurement, combined with surface properties by wettability test. The transmittance and surface resistance of CNT coated specimens were controlled by cyclic coating. After CNT coating process, CNT coated PET films showed hydrophobicity due to the nano-structure of CNT. High transparent and conductive PET films with CNT coating were obtained by triple cyclic coating. As cyclic coating increased, surface resistance of CNT coating decreased dramatically, whereas the transparent properties exhibited little lower. The CNT coating specimen was more stable than ITO coating under cyclic loading test.

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